

Hysteresis in Sorption of Water on Egg Albumin Heated to Different Temperatures

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Sorption-desorption hysteresis with water vapour on egg albumin both native and those previously heated at temperature of 50°, 80° and 110°, has been studied at 35° by means of quartz fibre spring technique. The hysteresis loop exhibited in the first cycle shows a tendency to decrease in size and finally disappears in subsequent cycles. The size of the loop decreases with the increase in the temperature of pre-heating. The results have been explained on the basis of the structure of proteins and the denaturation process.

EARLIER work on sorption hysteresis of water on proteins^{1,2} has either shown the absence of hysteresis effect, the sorption and desorption curves being coincident in the first cycle itself or the hysteresis phenomenon observed initially becomes smaller and disappears in the subsequent cycles. Benson and Richardson³ obtained a reproducible hysteresis loop in three successive cycles in the sorption and desorption of water on egg albumin. Rao and Das⁴ reported disappearance in the hysteresis loop of water on gelatin in subsequent cycles. These differences in the behaviour with regard to sorption and desorption hysteresis have been explained on the basis of the structure of proteins and the processes of swelling and shrinkage.

Studies on the effect of temperature on sorption hysteresis of proteins have not been made. The temperature or thermal heat may result in great changes in the ability of a protein to bind other substances and these changes reflect alterations in the molecular architecture which a sufficient understanding of the binding process, might enable us to decipher. Hence a systematic study of sorption-desorption hysteresis with water was undertaken by heating egg albumin at different temperatures and the results are presented in this paper.

Materials and Methods

The quartz fibre spring technique employed in the present work has been described elsewhere^{5,6}. The powdered egg albumin used was Merck's Albumin Ovi. The particle size was between those of 30 and 50 mesh British Standard Sieves.

The samples were prepared by heating native egg albumin at 50°, 80° and 110° in vacuo for 4 hours in each case. A series of sorptions and desorptions were carried out with water vapour on the samples at 35° in an air thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Sorption hysteresis on native egg albumin: The hysteresis loops obtained with native egg albumin

in the 1st, 4th and 5th cycles are shown in Fig. 1. The amounts of water taken at saturation pressure are 120.3, 125.4 and 124.0% respectively. There is a tendency for the decrease in size of the loop in successive cycles.

Fig. 1. Sorption and desorption of water on native egg albumin in the 1st, 4th and 5th cycles.

The protein is regarded^{7,8} as an assembly of helical polypeptide chains, cross linked here and there by disulphide bonds. The folding of the helices is maintained by hydrogen bonds between the peptide -N and -CO groups. In our view, sorption process is initially a surface adsorption of water, followed by a fast diffusion of the adsorbate into the interior of the protein molecules where the strongest binding sites are the free basic groups. The internal diffusion is accompanied by a progressive swelling of the protein net work and an increase in the binding to these active centres. The higher pressure finally leads to a multimolecular adsorption equivalent to solvation. If now, the swelling process is not reversible, this would account for hysteresis. These results are in agreement with those of Rao and Das⁵

who in their study with the sorption-desorption hysteresis on native egg albumin, reported decrease in size of the loop in successive cycles. Seehof⁹ *et al* also observed similar results.

It has been further observed that the total sorptive capacity from 1st to the 5th cycle practically remains the same, though the hysteresis loop has a great tendency to disappear. This has been attributed to the existence of pores in proteins⁵. The magnitude of the pore volume may be very small as compared with the total sorptive capacity of the material because the sorption of water by proteins is mostly by hydration. The decrease in size of the loop and ultimate disappearance in subsequent cycles is partially due to the gradual disappearance of the pores, which entrap water, because of the swelling of the protein network. The nature of the curves which is of type III of the BET classification¹⁰ suggests that this small pore volume is probably over shadowed by the water of hydration.

Fig. 2. Sorption and desorption of water on egg albumin heated at 50° in 1st, 3rd and 6th cycles.

Fig. 3. Sorption and desorption of water on egg albumin heated at 80° in 1st, 2nd and 5th cycles.

Fig. 4. Sorption and desorption of water on egg albumin heated at 110° in 1st, 4th and 5th cycles.

Effect of temperature : In the case of egg albumin heated at 50°, the loop decreases in size from 1st to the 6th cycle (Fig. 2). The amounts of water taken in each of these cycles are 120.3, 122.5 and 124.1% respectively. For egg albumin heated at 80°, the sorption-desorption studies were carried up to the fifth cycle (Fig. 3) and the sorption capacities in 1st, 2nd and 5th cycles are 120.6, 120.6 and 125.0% respectively. The hysteresis loops observed in 1st, 4th and 5th cycles with egg albumin heated at 110° have been shown in Fig. 4. The values at saturation pressure of water are 130.5, 132.6 and 132.6% respectively. In all these cases, the albumin was kept in contact with water vapour at saturation pressure for 2 days.

It is well known that almost any protein heated to 50°, 80° or 110° in vacuo for a few hours would be denatured any way. Recent ideas on protein denaturation^{11,12} indicate that the unfolding of the polypeptide chains might be the general process involved in all types of denaturation. Non-covalent bonds are ruptured to a greater or lesser extent with the subsequent exposure of buried group to the solvent and a probable loss of helical structure.

Pollard¹³ reported that heating results in the expansion of the molecule. He further observed that in the dry state, the thermal expansivity of egg albumin was found to be 1.6×10^{-4} fraction per degree centigrade, which is very large. It is so large that it cannot be due to the elongation of even very weak bonds and must correspond to a kind of swelling process in which secondary and tertiary structure enlarges.

If this is so, one might expect the amount of sorption to increase upon denaturation because the unfolding of the chains should make the sorption sites within the protein more accessible. The increase in sorption capacity from 120.3 to 130.5% when the pre-heating temperature is raised from 50° to 110°, is justified on this basis. An unfolded or open

network presumably could sorb polar vapour with little or no deformation and on the basis of the ideas already developed, there should be a very little or no hysteresis loop for water on denatured egg albumin. It is observed that as the temperature increases, the size of the loop decreases and at the highest temperature of 110°, the hysteresis loop almost disappears. Altman and Benson¹⁴ also made similar observations.

An attempt to ascertain, by solubility tests, the extent of loss of helical structure, failed. However, measurements of the area under the loop, obtained at different temperatures reveal that the denaturation starts at about 50° and is almost complete at 80°.

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